

The Implementation of Education Policies in Borena Pastoralist Area of Ethiopia: A Systematic Review of Literature

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Abstract: This literature review focuses on pastoralist area education policy implementation, its status, determinants, and how to improve the problems. It aims to clarify what implementing education policies in pastoralist areas entails in complex education systems to support pastoralist education policy implementation work, building on the literature and country experiences. An introduction delves into the reasons behind the need to update or create appropriate education policy implementation in the pastoralist area, which is defined as a purposeful and multidirectional change process aiming to put a specific policy into practice and which affects the pastoralist education system on several levels. The paper then analyzes the determinants that hinder or facilitate the implementation of pastoralist education policies for effective implementation. Based on the systematically reviewed data from different studies, the paper proposes a few recommendations that can guide researchers in their future research or studies on pastoralist education policy implementors more effectively.

Keywords: Education policy, Policy implementation, Education policy implementation, Borena pastoralist.

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1. Introduction

Why study education policy implementation in pastoralist areas? While pressures on pastoralist education systems grow to access education and deliver high-quality education and the number of reforms increases, governments and policymakers do not necessarily give much attention to their pastoralist education policy implementation. Education policy implementation in pastoralist areas is a complex, evolving process that involves many stakeholders and can result in failure if not well targeted. It is therefore crucial to understand it, clarify its determinants, and explore ways in which it can be more transparent and effective. This paper builds on the systematic review of literature to provide a definition of education policy implementation and its determinants and proposes some recommendations to support

education policy makers in the pastoralist area implementation process. This introductory section sets the scene to explain why it is important to analyze this topic now, what are some of the main challenges, and develops three questions that underpin the review of different studies. The section then describes the methodology used for the review, analysis of data, findings, results, discussions, and some recommendations for future research.

1.1 Background

Setting the stage for education policy implementation Between 2008 and 2014, OECD countries implemented 450 education changes (Volante, L., Fazio, X., & Ritzén, J., 2017). Given the rapidly changing economic, social, and demographic circumstances that surround education, attempts to adapt, enhance, and shape the future look justified. However, there is little evidence that education policy implementation has an effect because educational impacts are difficult to assess and rarely examined. Even when implementations have an impact, stakeholders are often dissatisfied with the results and hold policymakers accountable for them (Viennet, R., & Pont, B., 2017). Similarly, little is known about the actual procedures that result in, or are meant to result in, the desired pastoralist education policy implementation outcomes. Even though there is no agreement on the definition, these procedures "between the establishment of a policy and its effects in the world of action" (O'Toole Jr., 2000) are frequently referred to as policy implementation. There is a distinction to be made between enacting a policy bill or developing a strategy and making it a daily practice for teachers, school administrators, and local communities. Implementation specifics may be left to administrations and educators to work out, ultimately halting the reform process (Hess, 2013). Observing that policies are frequently not implemented as planned or with the desired results, governments, experts, and international organizations have started to recognize the importance of focusing more on education policy implementation processes (OECD, 2016). This is especially true and important in pastoralist parts of the world. Coordination concerns, inadequacy of organizational resources, actors' capacity, policy relevance, and quality issues are all challenges to executing education policy in pastoralist areas. However, as the education system has grown increasingly complicated, so have the problems of implementing reform. Education stakeholders are becoming more varied, as well as more vocal and ambitious about what pastoralist education systems should look like. The use of technology also contributes to the complexity of educational systems.

To improve decision-making that affects pastoral areas and the people who live there, a deeper understanding of pastoralism is required (Andreas et al., 2017). Borena pastoralists in Ethiopia are found in the low-lying areas of the southern Oromia regional state bordering northern Kenya. The main livelihood systems include pastoralism, smallholder agriculture, and ex-pastoralism: those who abandoned pastoralism and now survive on small income-generating activities (Behnke, 2007). Borena herders in Ethiopia live in marginalized, remote, and underdeveloped areas. In the pastoral areas of Borena, the illiteracy rate is very high, and most of their children do not go to school (UNICEF, Education and Resilience in Kenya's Arid Lands, 2015). Borena pastoralist communities in Ethiopia occupy the largest percentage of the total area of Oromia along the borders. The Borena herders are traditionally nomadic ethnic groups that are highly mobile, moving from one area to another in search of pasture and water for their livestock. They are well adapted to difficult terrain, extreme climates, and food insecurities. Borena herders move freely from one woreda to another, sometimes even crossing the country's international border, such as that with neighboring Kenya, in search of water and pasture for their cattle. During this movement, they take their children out of school, and student desertion and school closures are seen. Borena herders are distributed in the 13 districts of the Borena Zonal Area of Oromia Regional State in Ethiopia.

The pastoral communities of Borena do not have sufficient access to education or an adequate education policy implementation strategy to educate their children through the implementation of existing education policies in Ethiopia. However, the morality of parents is greatly emphasized by teaching their children to travel very far to find school. Borena herders are often described as food insecure and are associated with high levels of vulnerability. Basic social services such as education, electricity, roads and communications, access to credit, and insurance services are often less

developed than in other areas. Therefore, the Borena pastoral area is defined as the area with education indicators lower than the figures at the national level at any time due to the implementation of the country's education policy strategy. There are numerous factors that have a significant impact on pastoral education opportunities, which will be investigated in this study. If Ethiopia is to move towards better and more comprehensive development, it is recognized that attention must be paid to pastoral areas, which have a high incidence of poverty as well as low levels of educational attainment and participation. This study investigates the context in which education policy was developed and implemented in the Borena pastoral area of Ethiopia. The study investigates the practice of educational provision in these areas and assesses the impact of these educational policy implementations on access to pastoral education and the opportunity to reduce illiteracy in the area.

The way in which Ethiopian education policymakers address the challenges for the provision of education services in the pastoralist areas of Borena suggests the extent to which the rhetoric about herders reflects a genuine commitment among Ethiopian education policymakers to support the sustainability of pastoralists' livelihoods. Providing educational opportunities for pastoral children presents several unique challenges. Due to the low population densities and the relatively harsh and isolated environments that pastoralists inhabit, schools are few and far between, educational methodologies (curriculum), educational calendars, and qualified teachers are difficult to find. In addition, the mobility of herders and a family economy that has traditionally relied heavily on child labor increase the opportunity costs of herder children attending school.

1.2 Definition and Concept of Pastoralism

The world literature on pastoralism is extremely uneven and is shaped by socioeconomic, cultural, and political issues related to pastoralist communities, as well as the need for empirical data availability. Based on the limited knowledge available about grazing, different organizations and scholars define grazing in different ways. The FAO defines it as "extensive livestock production on pastures." The United Nations Convention No. 169 (1989) defines "ethnic identity, Indigenous and Tribal Peoples." Pastoralism is scientifically defined as "a member of social groups with a strong traditional association with livestock, where a substantial proportion of the group obtains more than 50% of the domestic consumption of livestock products or their sales, and where more than 90% of the consumption of animals is from natural pastures, and where the members of the households are responsible for the complete cycle of cattle raising."

Grazing is practiced mainly on grasslands that cover about a quarter of the world's surface (Follet, R.F., and D.A. Reed, 2010). It is closely associated with mobile herds and drylands (Robinson et al., 2011). Pastoralists use mobility as a basic strategy for developing their livelihoods and risk management systems. Although African pastoral ecosystems are the ancestral homeland of a substantial part of the population for whom pastoralism is a traditional way of life, pastoralism is far from static. Pastoralists in many areas are adapting to trends such as new economic opportunities and better access to modern means of communication (African Union, 2010).

Pastoralism is a key characteristic of the people in the Horn of Africa. It was estimated that approximately 20 million pastoralists live in the region where they generate significant migratory flows; they move seasonally, often across porous borders, in search of water, grazing land, better livelihoods, or simply safer environments (Ginetti, J., & Franck, T.; Anand, 2014).

The definition of pastoralism in the Ethiopian context is related to mobility, but this may not be true in the global context, where large herds of cattle are sometimes managed by sedentary households, simply allowing them to roam freely during the dry season. As people move away from drought, animal disease, or conflict and toward newly available resources, mobile devices cannot fully define pastoralism. Pastoralism can be thought of as a system of livestock and non-livestock activities connected through a network of social and economic relationships that extend well beyond lowland areas to highland economies and beyond the nation's borders (Linda, J., Sabates-Wheeler, R., & Kohnstamm, S., 2016). Pastoralism, the use of extensive grazing on rangelands for livestock production, is one of the key production, economic, and livelihood systems in the world's drylands. However, throughout much of its long history, its reputation

has been a grim one, with its practitioners marginalized by sedentary growers and urban dwellers. Pastoral societies have risen and fallen, fragmenting into isolated families or building world-spanning empires, and their demise is regularly heralded, often in the face of starkly contrary evidence of their persistence (Blench, 2001). According to Blench (2001), pastoralism never developed because population pressure on land remained limited; it was strongly associated with the presence of grasslands, but numerous grasslands can be found without pastoralists. But we totally disagree with this researcher because grazing can develop and disappear with the change of land use policy and the educational policy of the nation. In most of the world, except in Africa, agriculture appears to predate pastoralism, which developed later.

The existence of pastoralism has had complex relationships with the human history of hunter-gatherers, the green revolution, and the nature of land ownership in many parts of the world. Pastoralism developed in North and Central America after the Spanish era, when Amerindian peoples gained access to European ruminants or Old-World immigrants who settled and began farming in that area, which they have adopted in very contrasting ways (Melville, 1994). Then these towns were called "true pastoralism." The foundation of pastoralism has been much discussed, especially in older literature. The herding lifestyle developed from the herders' experience and surplus, as people accumulated too many animals to graze around a settlement throughout the year that herding developed. Similarly, as herders learned more about the relationships between particular types of ecology and the spread of livestock diseases, they gradually practiced seasonal migration of their animals from dangerous areas.

Many researchers and academics believe that herders' hardship and suffering are self-inflicted due to their apparent choice of a traditional lifestyle that inhibits their ability to innovate and adapt to recent global change, which is not true and is a misconception. to believe. Pastoralists do not suffer due to their choice of a traditional lifestyle but suffer due to the lack of inclusive government development policies, such as the implementation of education policies in Ethiopia. Pastoralists have multiple political identities: pastoralists, ranchers, regional, ethnic, religious, and "indigenous peoples" (Andreas et al., 2017).

1.3 The concept of education policy and implementation

1.3.1 Definition of Education Policy

Ball (2021) defines education policies as both systems of values and symbolic systems, ways of accounting for and legitimating political decisions and defining the public good. The set of concepts, norms, and legislation that regulate the education system in a specific country or region is referred to as education policy. Curriculum, finance, teacher training and recruiting, school infrastructure, and other aspects of education are all part of it. Political, social, and economic issues drive education policy, which can have a considerable impact on educational results and opportunities.

The set of rules, regulations, and guidelines that regulate the provision and management of education in a country or region is referred to as education policies (UNESCO, 2015). Education policies are important because they define the aims and objectives of education, outline the roles and responsibilities of various stakeholders, and identify the resources and tactics needed to attain the intended outcomes.

Political ideologies, cultural norms, economic situations, and social agendas can all have a substantial impact on education policies across countries and regions (European Commission, 2020). Most education policies, however, have common elements, such as the need to offer fair access to education, promote academic success, and prepare students for the needs of today's workforce.

Several worldwide trends, including the rising use of technology in education, the growing desire for lifelong learning and the need to face the challenges of globalization and climate change, have affected education policies in recent years (UNESCO, 2015). This demonstrates that many types of education policies are currently being adopted in various parts of the world to meet societal demands and enhance progress. As governments and education stakeholders adjust to changing social, economic, and technical situations, education policies are always altering.

When we come to pastoral education policies, they are intended to meet the educational demands of pastoralist communities. These programs recognize that pastoralist communities have distinct cultural and socioeconomic circumstances that necessitate customized educational approaches. Among the most important pastoralist education policies are:

Inclusion of pastoralist knowledge and practices in the curriculum: Pastoralist education policies emphasize traditional pastoralist knowledge and practices and strive to incorporate them into the formal curriculum. This method ensures that pastoralist children can learn in a way that is culturally relevant and suitable.

Flexible and mobile education: Pastoralist education policies recognize that pastoralist communities are frequently nomadic and require adaptable education systems to meet their shifting demands. Mobile schools, distance learning programs, and the use of technology to convey educational information are examples of this method.

Multilingual education: Pastoralist education policies recognize the importance of language in education and strive to provide multilingual education that represents the pastoralist communities' linguistic variety. This method ensures that pastoralist youngsters can learn in their mother tongue while also improving their skills in the national language.

Community involvement in education: Pastoralist education policies value community involvement in education and strive to incorporate pastoralist communities in the conception, implementation, and assessment of educational programs. This strategy guarantees that pastoralist communities feel ownership and involvement in the schooling system.

1.3.2 Definition of Policy Implementation

The process of putting policy into action is referred to as policy implementation (Weber, 2015). In this regard, a variety of actions, such as resource planning, organization, and coordination, as well as monitoring and evaluating progress, A comprehensive grasp of the policy goals, as well as the resources and capacity required to attain them, is required for effective policy implementation. Political will, administrative competence, and stakeholder participation are frequently influencing factors.

When it comes to pastoralist education policy implementation, there are various problems, such as inadequate resources, logistical issues, and cultural hurdles. However, numerous ways for overcoming these obstacles and ensuring the effective implementation of pastoralist education policy have been devised. Among these strategies are:

Targeted teacher training: Pastoralist education regulations necessitate that teachers have a thorough awareness of pastoralist culture as well as educational demands. Targeted teacher education programs can provide instructors with the skills and knowledge they need to effectively teach pastoralist children.

Mobile schools: Mobile schools can be utilized to educate pastoralist youngsters who are constantly on the move. These schools can be established in temporary settings and moved as pastoralist communities relocate.

Community involvement: The involvement of the community is important to the successful implementation of pastoralist education policy. By involving pastoralist communities in the conception, execution, and assessment of educational programs, it is possible to ensure that the programs are culturally relevant and suitable.

Use of technology: Some of the logistical issues associated with adopting pastoralist education policy can be overcome through the use of technology. Distance learning programs and smartphone apps, for example, can be utilized to give educational information to pastoralist communities in remote areas.

1.3.3 Concepts of Education Policy Implementation

The concept of implementation in education is ambiguous since it can refer to either the strict concept of implementation or a much larger conceptualization that encompasses not only the process but also the elements that surround it.

According to Fullan M. (2015), the concept pertains to the goal of implementation, which is to bring about the intended change.

Fullan's perspective is completed by Hoving (2006) and Aikman (2011), who emphasize that implementation is a construct of various processes and that context determines how implementation evolves.

The broad definition of education policy implementation. Thus, we defined education policy implementation as a deliberate and multidirectional change process aimed at putting a given policy into reality and which may affect an education system on multiple levels.

- Implementation is purposeful in the sense that the process is intended to change education in accordance with some policy objectives.
- It is multidirectional in the sense that it may be influenced by players at different stages of the educational system.
- It is contextualized in the sense that institutions and societal shocks and trends (i.e., in culture, demography, politics, and economy) affect the education system and the ways in which a policy is shaped and translates in the education sector.

Education policy implementation can be technically defined as government actions in relation to educational practices as well as how governments approach the production and delivery of education in a specific system. To be sure, others advocate for a broader definition of education policy implementation, recognizing that corporate players or other institutions, such as international and non-governmental organizations, can initiate educational policy implementation. This study, on the other hand, focuses on education policies developed by public authorities (whether at the national, regional, or local levels) for the delivery of public education in the Borena pastoral area.

Education policy implementation is the process of putting education policies into action. It entails turning policy aims into action and ensuring that policies are implemented successfully and efficiently at the school, district, and national levels. Education policy implementation in pastoralist areas like Borena can be difficult since it frequently involves several stakeholders and necessitates cooperation across multiple levels of government and the education system.

2. Aims of the review

Stemming from the literature and contextual characteristics of pastoralists in Ethiopia, the overall aim of this review was to investigate systematically how the implementation of education policy in the Borena pastoralist area has been conducted during the 1994–2023 period of gaps in Ethiopia. Specifically, the following questions were addressed:

1. What types of implementations of education policy in pastoralist areas have been conducted?
2. What are the foci of the implementation of education policy activities in pastoralist areas?
3. What are the factors affecting the implementation of education policy activities?
4. How is the implementation of education policy activities being employed and evaluated?

What are the outcomes of these IEPPA activities?

3. Methodology and methods

To answer these questions, I used a systematic literature review, locating and synthesizing primary research studies on pastoralist education systems around the world and specifically the pastoralist area of Ethiopia. According to Gough, D., and Richardson, M. (2018), a systematic literature review has an "explicit, rigorous methodology," making the review results "accountable and open to criticism." In conducting this review, I attempted to employ a systematic approach to synthesizing available evidence to inform those who are engaged in the decision-making process that may help the Ethiopian government work on vast pastoralist areas in the country. In addition, since this type of review can offer a complementary mechanism for analyzing and mapping the information, it is possible to gain insights into certain aspects of IEPPA while having a general overview of IEPPA practice inside the country over a time span. Indeed, I

consider systematic review a useful and reliable methodology, if conducted rigorously, for delivering evidence for policymakers and practitioners in both IEPPA and the Borena pastoralist area of Ethiopia. I determined the protocol for this review by adopting procedures based on the general guidelines of the collaboration (Collaboration, 2017). Accordingly, I (1) followed a predetermined set of inclusion and exclusion criteria, (2) screened and extracted data, (3) assessed the relevance of the reviewed studies, and (4) synthesized the results. I classify and synthesize the data related to IEPPA and its outcomes extracted from the studies under review, which will help me know the evaluation outcomes.

3.1 Inclusion/exclusion criteria

I developed four inclusion criteria to determine the relevant studies from my preliminary search: (1) published between 1994 and 2023; (2) contained in the abstracts at least two and above keywords: (a) policy, (b) implementation, (c) education, (d) pastoralist, and (e) at least in the pastoralist area or rural area (3) written in English; and (4) report original data. A checklist based on these criteria was created to screen the studies. This review used one of the most popular electronic databases, which is 'Google Scholar', the most widely used database in education and academic research. The search terms included the following:

1. policy or law or regulation or agreement and
2. Implementation, execution, application, and
3. Policy implementation, policy execution, policy application,
4. Australia, Asia (3 countries), Europe (2 countries), North America (2 countries), South America (2 countries), Ethiopia, Somalia, Kenya, Tanzania, Eritrea, Gabon, Congo, Nigeria, Mali, Algeria, and Sudan

3.2 Data screening and extraction

As summarized in Fig. 1, among 457 abstracts from the publication sources in the databases and web sites, 278 abstracts were excluded because they were unrelated to IEPPA; 89 were excluded for not being set in pastoralist education; and 11 were excluded for not being in the context of pastoralist education. 79 abstracts met all of the requirements and were cross-screened for the second time with direct reference to their full texts. Four papers were excluded for being secondary source studies on IEPPA. The process resulted in 75 publications for independent, detailed evaluation. Data from the included studies were then extracted onto Microsoft Excel, containing nine relevant categories drawn from the research questions, including pastoralist area, study objectives, IEPPA types, focus, evaluation (yes/no), how to evaluate, outcomes (yes/no), outcomes, and recommendations/implications. All data extraction was checked twice to enhance reliability.

3.3 Study relevance assessment

I assessed the 75 articles in terms of their relevance to the current review's objectives. I followed loosely the "weight of evidence," which refers to a framework for the appraisal of the quality and relevance of evidence (Gough, 2021), in order to decide the extent of relevance in determining which studies were to be retained. Accordingly, three papers were excluded because of their irrelevance to my research questions, i.e., having data for only two out of ten categories in the data extraction matrix. The remaining 72 studies were then included for the final review. Among these, highly relevant studies ($n = 52$; 72.2%) had data for more than six categories out of eight. Each of nine medium-relevant studies ($n = 12$; 16.7%) met four or five categories, and six papers ($n = 8$; 11.1%) were classified as having low relevance with three categories.

Figure 3 1: Literature search and article selection for review

4. Data synthesis

As mentioned earlier, I tabulated all relevant information from the included studies on a matrix with categories corresponding to different aspects of the research questions. The reviewers together went through the information under each category and unanimously synthesized the results across the studies. The main aim of this cross-study synthesis will be to seek common overall trends and explore the implementation of education policies in the pastoralist area on the basis of the available evidence collected.

5. Findings

I have come up with the following findings which fall into five categories: (1) Nations of pastoralist education policies implementations (2) Types of pastoralist education policies actively in action; (3) Focus of pastoralist education policies activities; and (4) Factors affecting the implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas 5. Evaluation and outcomes of pastoralist education policy implementation.

5.1 Nations of pastoralist education policies and implementations

Pastoralism has been a traditional way of life for many communities around the world, particularly in Africa, Asia, and the Middle East. However, pastoralist communities face unique challenges in accessing education and other social services. In recent years, there have been efforts to develop and implement policies that address these challenges and improve access to education for pastoralist communities.

Globally, of the 20 countries under review, some articles include more than two countries: Australia, Europe, Asia, North America, and South America, which are the first ranking countries in facilitating pastoralist education policies and implementation strategies effectively. Most countries on the continent of Africa have failed to initiate pastoralist education policies and strategies, except for Kenya, Tanzania, and Nigeria. There has been growing recognition of the importance of education for pastoralist communities. In 2018, the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) published a report on the education of nomadic and pastoralist communities. The report highlights the challenges that these communities face in accessing education and presents a series of recommendations for improving educational opportunities for pastoralist communities. Articles from those countries under review: 38 papers (52.8%) have effective pastoralist education policies implementation strategies; seven papers (9.7%) have medium pastoralist education policies implementation strategies; and the rest of the 27 papers (37.5%) have no identified pastoralist education policies implementation strategies. It is worth noting that the collected data on the implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas is evidence of what I found in published papers within the limits of this review and is not necessarily an actual portrayal of what has been happening in the countries in focus. **See table below:**

Table 5 1: Shows the papers reviewed with responses of IEPPA

No.	Continent/countries	Number of papers	Have IEPPA	Have no IEPPA	Effectiveness of IEPPA		
					Highly effective	Medium	Low
1	Australia	4	4		4		
2	Europe (2)	4	4		4		
3	Asia (3)	9	9		8	1	
4	N. America (2)	1	1		1		
5	S. America (2)	2	2		2		
	Africa- Eastern						
6	Ethiopia	8		8			8
7	Kenya	12	12		12		
8	Tanzania	7	7		7		
9	Sudan	3		3			3
10	Somalia	5		5			5
11	Eritrea	3	3				3
	Western Africa						
12	Nigeria	6	6			5	1
13	Algeria	2		2		1	1
14	Mali	2		2			2
	Central Africa						
15	Congo	3		3			3
16	Gabon	1		1			1
	Total	72	48	24	38	7	27

In Ethiopia, pastoralist education policies were established and implemented to meet the issues encountered by pastoralist communities. These policies aim to improve access to education for pastoralist children and to ensure that the education provided is relevant to their needs and culture. In 2015, the Ethiopian government launched the Pastoralist Education Strategy, which outlines a series of measures to improve access to education for pastoralist communities in

Ethiopia (MoE, 2015). These measures include the construction of schools in pastoralist areas, the development of culturally sensitive curricula, and the recruitment and training of teachers from pastoralist communities.

However, there have also been criticisms of the implementation of pastoralist education policies in Ethiopia. Some scholars argue that these policies have not been effectively implemented and that there is a need for greater consultation and participation of pastoralist communities in the development and implementation of education policies. Despite these challenges, there is growing recognition of the importance of education for pastoralist communities, and efforts are being made to improve access to education and ensure that the education provided is relevant and culturally appropriate.

From the findings, mostly all developed countries have pastoralist education policies and better implementation strategies of education policies in pastoralist areas by fulfilling our criteria for reviewing the studies screened. Those countries on the African continent have little or no initiation into pastoralist education policies and their implementation strategies.

5.2 Types of pastoralist education policies actively in action

I categorized the education policies of the pastoralist areas of the countries under review into three main types: (1) have pastoralist education policies; (2) have pastoralist education policies embedded in the other education policies of the country; and (3) have no pastoralist education policies (see Table 5.2).

Table 5 2: Data collected for IEPPA

No.	Continent/countries	Number of papers	Have IEPPA	Have no separate IEPPA
1	Australia	4	4	
2	Europe (2)	4	4	
3	Asia (3)	9	9	
4	N. America (2)	1	1	
5	S. America (2)	2	2	
	Africa- Eastern			
6	Ethiopia	8		8
7	Kenya	12	12	
8	Tanzania	7	7	
9	Sudan	3		3
10	Somalia	5		5
11	Eritrea	3	3	
	Western Africa			
12	Nigeria	6	6	
13	Algeria	2		2
14	Mali	2		2
	Central Africa			
15	Congo	3		3
16	Gabon	1		1
Total		72	48	24

Pastoralist education policies are designed to address the unique challenges faced by pastoralist communities in accessing education (Ng’asike, 2019). These policies vary depending on the context and specific needs of the community. From

the findings, out of 72 papers, 48 (66.7%) reported there are IEPPA strategies, primarily in developed and some developing countries. Among 72 articles, 24 papers (33.3%) report that those countries have not initiated the IEPPA strategy separately yet but are using the same education policies as the country, which is not relevant to the lifestyle of pastoralist society. Most African countries have not developed pastoralist education policies in a pastoralist context. For example, Ethiopia, Mali, Gabo, Sudan, Somalia, Algeria, and the Congo do not have separate pastoralist education policies. But they are embedded in their main education policies. Unfortunately, I have not identified papers that report countries with no education policies at all. Here are some types of pastoralist education policies that are actively in action globally:

1. **Bilingual education:** Bilingual education policies aim to improve access to education for pastoralist children by providing instruction in both their native language and the national language. This approach recognizes the importance of preserving the cultural and linguistic heritage of pastoralist communities while also providing them with the skills and knowledge needed to participate in wider society.
2. **Mobile schools:** Mobile schools are an innovative approach to providing education to pastoralist communities in remote areas. These schools are designed to be portable and can be moved to different locations depending on the needs of the community. They often use flexible and non-traditional teaching methods to accommodate the needs of pastoralist children, who may have irregular attendance due to their nomadic lifestyle.
3. **Culturally sensitive curricula:** Culturally sensitive curricula aim to provide pastoralist children with an education that is relevant to their culture and way of life. These curricula incorporate traditional knowledge and practices into the educational content, helping to promote the value of pastoralism and its contribution to society.

In Ethiopia, the Pastoralist Education Strategy, launched in 2015, is a comprehensive policy that aims to improve access to education for pastoralist communities. The strategy includes a range of measures, including the construction of schools in pastoralist areas, the development of culturally sensitive curricula, and the recruitment and training of teachers from pastoralist communities. But this strategy is not fully in action due to the failure of regional governments to implement it as required.

5.3 Focus of pastoralist education policy implementation globally and in Ethiopia

The synthesis of the 72 studies revealed that the primary focus of the IEPPA of all paper reports (100%) was mainly on the accessibility of education, the geographical landscape problems of pastoralist areas, and the challenges faced by mobility in pastoralist societies. On the other hand, among 72 studies, 42 papers (58.3%) report the issue of education relevance, which is mainly a big concern for the pastoralist education systems. There are 25 studies (34.7%) that report on the IEPPA quality assurance strategies. See Table 5.3.

Table 5 3: Analysis of focus of pastoralist education policy and its implementation status

Name of country/ continent	Accessibility	Relevance of education	Quality of educa- tion	Geographical location	Mobility of the society
Australia	4	3	3	4	4
Europe	4	3	3	4	4
Asia	9	6	5	9	9
N. America	1	1	1	1	1
S. America	2	2	2	2	2
Africa- Eastern					
Ethiopia	8	4		8	8
Kenya	12	8	4	12	12

Tanzania	7	5	4	7	7
Sudan	3	1		3	3
Somalia	5	3		5	5
Eritrea	3	1		3	3
Western Africa					
Nigeria	6	3	2	6	6
Algeria	2	1	1	2	2
Mali	2			2	2
Central Africa					
Congo	3	1		3	3
Gabon	1			1	1
Total	72	42	25	72	72

Pastoralist education policies aim to improve the educational opportunities and outcomes of pastoralist communities. These policies should recognize the unique cultural and economic contexts of pastoralist communities and seek to address the challenges that hinder not only access to education but also relevance and quality of education in pastoralist areas. The implementation of pastoralist education policies globally and in Ethiopia has focused on several key areas. The most common area of focus has been to increase access to education for pastoralist children. This has involved initiatives such as building schools in remote areas, providing transportation to schools, and offering flexible learning opportunities that accommodate the nomadic lifestyle of pastoralists. This is true when we see developed countries and some developing countries like America, Europe, and Asia. But it is far reaching when we see most African countries like Mali, Ethiopia, Eritrea, and Sudan. Another area of focus that has been seen is improving the quality of education provided to pastoralist children. This has involved training teachers to work in multicultural and multilingual environments and developing curricula that are relevant to the needs and experiences of pastoralist children. It is also mostly true for developed countries and some developing countries like America, Europe, Australia, and Asia. But most African countries focus only on education accessibility, except for some advances in Kenya, Tanzania, Algeria, and Nigeria, which have made remarkable changes to pastoralist education quality assurance. The rest of the countries, like Ethiopia, Sudan, Mali, Gabon, Eritrea, and Somalia, do not take any action on the quality of pastoralist education.

In addition, pastoralist education policies in most countries sought to address the social and economic factors that contribute to low education attainment among pastoralists. For example, policies have aimed to address poverty and gender inequalities that can limit access to education. These initiatives are also limited in most African countries and some Asian countries. While most developed countries and some developing countries have sought to promote bilingual education and to recognize and value the cultural knowledge and practices of pastoralist communities, many African countries like Nigeria, Sudan, Kenya, Tanzania, Eritrea, Gabon, and Mali are still doing less.

In Ethiopia, the federal government has tried to implement several policies and initiatives aimed at improving pastoralist education. For example, the Ethiopian government launched the Pastoralist Education Strategy in 2011 (Mohamed, 2019), which aimed to improve access to and quality of education for pastoralist communities. The strategy included initiatives such as building schools in remote areas, providing school feeding programs, and offering flexible learning opportunities. In addition, the federal government has promoted bilingual education and has worked to empower pastoralist communities to participate in the education system. Education for pastoralist children necessitates particular arrangements and interventions that are compatible with the transhumant pastoralist community's way of life. Oromia regional governments appear to have failed to prioritize the development of region-specific and context-specific education delivery models (USAID, 2019).

Despite these efforts, challenges remain in implementing pastoralist education policies in Ethiopia and globally. These challenges include limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, education qualities, relevance of education, and cultural barriers, which are mostly challenging in all developing countries, especially in Africa. However, ongoing efforts to address these challenges and promote the education of pastoralist communities are crucial for improving their economic and social outcomes.

5.4 Factors affecting the implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas

Several variables influence how education programs are implemented in pastoralist settings. From the analysis of the 72 articles, I categorized them into nine (9) categories and evaluated their impacts accordingly. These are: 1. Mobility 2. Education quality 3. Accessibility (due to geographical landscape) 4. Relevance 5. Early child marriage 6. Lack of school meals 7. Conflicts and drought; 8. Education Methodology 9. Teacher training and in-service development.

Among the 72 assessed articles, all (100%) assure that mobility and accessibility are the crucial factors affecting IEPPA around the globe, and one category may be included in two or more categories. Among 72 articles, 26 papers (36%) report education relevance as a factor affecting IEPPA, and 18 papers (25%) report education quality of pastoralist areas as factors affecting IEPPA, 19 papers (26.4%) report Early child marriage as a factor affecting IEPPA, especially in Africa, 8 papers (11%) report Absence of school meals as factors affecting IEPPA (especially in Africa), 15 papers (20.8%) report conflicts and drought as factors affecting IEPPA, and 26 papers (36%) report education methodologies as factors affecting IEPPA, and 22 papers (30.5%) report teacher training and in-service development systems as factors affecting IEPPA (in some countries in Africa). See Table 5.4.

Table 5 4: Analysis of the factors affecting IEPPA

Name of country/ continent	Mobility	Geo-graphical landscape	education methodology	education relevance	Education quality	early Child marriage	lack of school meals	Conflicts and drought	teacher training
Australia	4	4	2	2	2				
Europe	4	4	1	2	2				
Asia	9	9	5	4	5				
N. America	1	1		1	1				
S. America	2	2		2	2				
Africa- Eastern									
Ethiopia	8	8	3	1		4	5	2	6
Kenya	12	12	5	4	2	2		3	2
Tanzania	7	7	3	4	3	5		2	3
Sudan	3	3	2	1		2		2	2
Somalia	5	5	1	1		4	2	1	3
Eritrea	3	3	1	1		1	1	1	2
Western Africa									
Nigeria	6	6	2	2	1			1	1
Algeria	2	2		1				1	
Mali	2	2							
Central Africa								1	2
Congo	3	3				1			
Gabon	1	1	1					1	1
Total	72	72	26	26	18	19	8	15	22

6. Evaluation and outcomes of pastoralist education policy implementation

The section below presents findings regarding the evaluation of pastoralist education policies, their implementation strategies, their evaluation methods, and IEPPA outcomes, with examples taken from the included studies.

6.1 Evaluation and outcomes of IEPPA

The search identified 56 studies (77.8%) that demonstrated various approaches to evaluating IEPPA. The majority relied on surveys and secondary data analysis to get research results. The remaining studies evaluated education accessibility using qualitative methods. In short, despite various approaches to evaluating IEPPA, I found that most evaluations have been qualitative and focused on education access rather than investigating many other education policy implementation strategies.

Overall, all studies highlight some challenges and successes of implementing education policies in the pastoralist area, depending on their research context and area. They agreed on the need for further research to better understand these challenges and to identify effective strategies for improving the implementation of education policies in the pastoralist area. Such research could inform the development of policies and programs that address the specific needs and challenges of pastoralist communities and help to improve access to quality education for all children. However, further discussion about evaluation approaches is presented in the "Discussion" section below.

7. Discussion and implications for practice

This part discusses some important themes that emerged from the above findings and offers some recommendations for practice.

7.1 Nations implementing education policies in pastoralist areas

As mentioned previously, this review may not capture a true account of what is actually happening in the pastoralist area of the world. I identified in the literature that almost all developed and some developing countries are the leading countries from which empirical evidence on IEPPA could be obtained. It should be noted, however, that some authors of those papers were not necessarily researchers from the countries of study and may not have a better understanding of the situations in pastoralist areas. Surprisingly, however, most of the studies under review reported the problem of education accessibility and the mobility of the pastoralist society as a big issue. Some of the studies almost ignore the relevance and quality of education issues in the pastoralist area. Most of the studies focus on the lifestyle of the pastoralist community, the geographical landscape of the area, and the limitations of the resources available to the pastoralist community, especially in most African and some Asian countries.

The findings may suggest that IEPPA has not been the focus of most countries in the world due to the small number of pastoralist populations compared to the other societies in the country and the need for huge resources that the implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas may need. But the reality is that providing education for the pastoralist community is not such a huge challenge if governments, other stockholders, and communities coordinate and try to provide education to pastoralist children by making suitable IEPPA strategies that may change the socioeconomic issues of the pastoralist area. This is because we have seen countries focused on IEPPA strategies succeed, like most countries in the west and east of the globe, as well as some countries like Kenya and Tanzania, which have had good experiences in creating suitable strategies for the IEPPA.

The implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas requires a nuanced approach that reflects the unique characteristics and needs of these communities. Some key notions for implementing education policies in pastoralist areas are:

1. **Understanding the pastoralist lifestyle:** Policies should be developed with a clear understanding of the pastoralist lifestyle, including their nomadic way of life, their reliance on livestock, and their cultural practices. This understanding will help policymakers tailor educational programs that meet the specific needs of these communities.
2. **Involving the community:** Community involvement is essential for the successful implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas. Policies should be developed in consultation with the local community, with input from leaders, parents, and teachers. This will ensure that policies are relevant and that stakeholders are invested in their success.
3. **Providing access to quality education:** Policies must aim to provide access to quality education for all children in pastoralist areas, including boys and girls, children with disabilities, and those from disadvantaged backgrounds. This might involve developing schools that are mobile, flexible, and able to move with pastoralist families.
4. **Promoting bilingual education:** Most pastoralist communities have their own language, which may not be widely spoken outside their communities. Policies should aim to promote bilingual education, which recognizes and values the pastoralist language and culture while also providing education that is relevant to a wider society.
5. **Addressing gender inequalities:** Gender inequalities persist in pastoralist communities, with girls being particularly vulnerable to exclusion from education. Policies should aim to address this by promoting girls' education, providing safe and secure schooling environments, and addressing the social and economic factors that limit access to education for girls.
6. **Strengthening the teaching workforce:** A lack of trained teachers who understand pastoralist culture may jeopardize the quality of education in these communities. Policies should aim to develop a cadre of trained local teachers who are familiar with pastoralist culture and can connect with students and their families.
7. **Encouraging parental involvement:** Policies should aim to encourage parental involvement in their children's education, recognizing that parents have a critical role to play in supporting their children's learning. This might involve developing programs that help parents understand the importance of education and provide them with the tools and skills they need to support their children's learning at home.

Overall, implementing education policies in pastoralist areas requires an understanding of the unique characteristics and needs of these communities and a commitment to working with them to develop policies and programs that are relevant, culturally appropriate, and sustainable.

7.2 Types and focus of education policy implementation in pastoralist areas

The findings suggested that IEPPA is successful if the government establishes suitable strategies and focuses on resolving all its determinates in different aspects. The government should make pastoralist policies and implementation strategies relevant to the lifestyle and geographical landscape of the pastoralist area and suitable education methodologies for the children.

Education policies in pastoralist areas can vary depending on the country, region, and the specific needs and challenges of the community. However, some common types and foci of education policy implementation in pastoralist areas are:

1. **Basic education:** Many pastoralist communities lack access to basic education, which is often a result of limited infrastructure, inadequate resources, socio-cultural beliefs and practices, and conflict. Basic education policies in pastoralist areas prioritize increasing enrollment, attendance, and retention rates for both boys and girls. Such policies may include building schools, providing transportation, supplying textbooks, and hiring local teachers who are trained to address the specific needs of the community.

2. **Alternative education:** In some pastoralist areas, the traditional modes of education may not be feasible due to seasonal mobility, migration, and other social and economic factors. Alternative education policies focus on providing access to non-formal education, including community-based learning centers, mobile schools, radio-based instruction, and distance learning programs that incorporate pastoralist knowledge systems and practices.
3. **Equity and inclusion:** Education policies in pastoralist areas prioritize equity and inclusion by addressing the significant disparities in educational outcomes between pastoralist and non-pastoralist populations. Such policies may include affirmative action programs, scholarships, and incentives for the most disadvantaged pastoralist communities.
4. **Gender equality:** This program seeks to enhance girls' involvement and retention in school, which is frequently hampered by socio-cultural attitudes and practices that value early marriage, domestic work, and other gender-specific responsibilities. Such policies may include targeted interventions, such as girls' boarding schools, female teachers, and awareness-raising campaigns that mobilize communities and families to support girls' education.
5. **Multilingual education:** Many pastoralist communities use multiple languages, and this can pose a challenge for educational access and achievement. Multilingual education policies in pastoralist areas aim to ensure that students can learn in their mother tongue while also acquiring proficiency in national languages. Such policies may include bilingual and multilingual programs, training for teachers in language instruction, and the development of culturally relevant instructional materials.
6. **Vocational education and training (VET) policies** are designed to address the unique economic challenges of pastoralist communities by providing skills and knowledge that are relevant to their way of life. VET policies in pastoralist areas prioritize skills development in animal husbandry, crop production, natural resource management, and other livelihood sectors.

Overall, education policies in pastoralist areas must be designed with a deep understanding of the socio-cultural, economic, and environmental factors that influence the community's education system. By prioritizing equity, inclusion, and effective coordination between key stakeholders, education policies in pastoralist areas can improve educational outcomes and promote sustainable development for pastoralist communities.

7.3 Evaluation of the Implementation of Education Policies in the Pastoralist Area

It is obvious from our findings that not all studies reported concrete evaluations of the IEPPA activities conducted. This suggests that the evaluation stage, which should be a central component, tends to be missing from the agenda of many IEPPA activities. Moreover, most examined IEPPA activities relied on the mobility and accessibility of the pastoralists and pastoralist area education systems, ignoring the relevance and quality of education in the area. In this respect, the IEPPA objectives may not have been truly fulfilled. In those cases where there is no evaluation, according to Morgan, J., Sengedorj, T. (2023), and Mtey, this is a common problem with IEPPA in other geographical areas of the world. Given that implementing evaluations requires time and resources, Kiminza (2022) and many other authors have advised that pastoralist and IEPPA practitioners use relevant and insightful evaluations to gauge precisely IEPPA outcomes and thus help plan more effective pastoralist education systems.

Additionally, Van Hoek (2001) suggested using evaluation triangulation, which involves extensive effort. This is an ideal approach to obtaining highly credible evaluation outcomes of IEPPA and measuring the effectiveness of IEPPA interventions, especially if conducted over the long term. However, these resource-intensive approaches appear impractical in many cases, such as with huge resource needs and a larger pastoralist area. Thus, it is recommended for IEPPA practitioners, education leaders, and policymakers to consider various factors in applying an evaluation framework relevant to the IEPPA format and focus.

8. Conclusion and Recommendation

After conducting a systematic review of the literature on the implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas, it is clear that there are significant challenges that must be addressed in order to ensure the successful implementation of education policies in these areas. The key challenges identified in the literature include inadequate infrastructure, limited access to education, quality assurance problems, the irrelevance of IEPPA strategies, early marriage, human resource development problems, and conflicts.

In order to overcome these challenges and improve the implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas, several recommendations can be made. Firstly, there is a need to invest in infrastructure such as schools, roads, and water supply systems to improve access to education in these areas. Secondly, there is a need to address language and cultural barriers by providing education in local languages and training teachers in these languages. Thirdly, it is important to involve the pastoralist communities in policy development and implementation to ensure that their needs and perspectives are taken into account.

Additionally, it is recommended that education policies in pastoralist areas be flexible and adaptive to the unique cultural and environmental contexts of these areas. The policies should also prioritize the development of skills and knowledge that are relevant to pastoralist livelihoods and promote gender equality and social inclusion.

In conclusion, the implementation of education policies in pastoralist areas is a complex and challenging task that requires collaboration and partnership between governments, communities, and other stakeholders. By addressing the challenges identified in this review and implementing the recommendations provided, it is possible to improve access to education and promote sustainable development in pastoralist areas.

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NB: Except references with Asterix (*), all the rest references are the references included in the systematic Review

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Haro Begeja Morge, born in the Dillo district of Borena pastoralist area in the Oromia regional state of Ethiopia, is a highly experienced individual in the field of education. With a strong background in administrative aspects, particularly in the Borena pastoralist area. Haro has dedicated his career to improving educational opportunities for the local community. He furthered his academic pursuits by obtaining a Master's degree in Comparative Education from China, solidifying his position as an emerging academic scholar.

